

Human flourishing and social service in engineering students

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Abstract

It is imperative to design innovative interdisciplinary didactics for engineering students as a way to: 1) the contribution of this valuable talent to social service during all stages of university education and, 2) stimulate human flourishing as an indispensable element from their youth for personal and professional development by improving the lives of others. Tec de Monterrey's Educational Model is based on disciplinary and transversal competencies, and on Challenge-Based Learning. The training unit called *Semana Tec con sentido humano "El rol de mi profesión el desempeño de mi profesión" y "Construcción de comunidades inclusivas a través de la dignidad humana"* (Tec Week with Human Sense: The role of integrity in the performance of my profession and Building Inclusive Communities from Human Dignity). was designed with eight hours of daily activity for weeks 6/18 and 12/18 of the semester. Students collaborate in an interdisciplinary manner at least twice during their university life in the concrete solution of a social problem to develop the competency Ethical and civic commitment in the sub-competencies: a) Integrity, and b) Recognition and empathy. With the accompaniment and guidance of the professor, and the training partner -a public or private instance- with a need. This Tec Week is integrated with theoretical frameworks and current indicators on human dignity, ethics, legality, transparency, diversity and inclusion, corruption, among others. Through a dialogue with the training partner about its mission and service, and direct immersion in the problem to be solved, engineering students design prototypes that are implemented. The evaluation of the development of transversal competencies in students is conducted by the professor. Since 2019, in the 32 campuses of Tec de Monterrey there are approximately 1000 groups in Tec Weeks with Human Sense with approximately 5000 prototypes. This article for PAAE/ALE 2025 presents the theoretical foundation of Human Flourishing, the didactic design, types of training partners and recent examples of prototypes of the authors.

Keywords: Interdisciplinarity, human flourishing, social service, transversal competencies.

1 Introduction

Engineering education must offer innovative paths that connect professional development and active learning not only in the specialized knowledge of engineering, but with equal importance, with the development of transversal ethical and citizenship competencies. That is why it must be ensured that the teaching/learning process is a solid bridge that connects the needs of society with the solutions that can be provided by the various engineering disciplines through ethical training throughout professional education. For this purpose, it is necessary that within the universities, the objective is to establish a close relationship with a permanent dialogue between different instances and academic departments with didactic projects that manage to potentiate the formative sense of each one of them in the integral profile of the students. This objective will be achieved through the interdisciplinary design of innovative didactic models and techniques that manage to build in a complete way the professional and formative profile that today is needed from future graduates. This is the case of the present work in which the Department of Humanistic Studies, the Department of Social Service and all 18 engineering careers of the Monterrey Campus are united in the same project: Tec Week with Human Sense: Building Inclusive Communities from human dignity.

The present work proposes as a research assumption:

"Students of engineering careers discover their human flourishing from their university stage when performing a social service with the didactic design of the "*Semana Tec son sentido humano: construcción de comunidades inclusivas desde la dignidad humana*" (Tec Week with Human Sense: Building Inclusive Communities from Human Dignity), and, simultaneously, develop the transversal competence of recognition and empathy; both elements will shape their professional profile when they join the working world with their professional degree".

The following objectives:

General objective: To evidence that human flourishing can be discovered by engineering students from their university life through social service.

Specific objectives:

- 1) Explain the didactic model of the Tec Week are human sense.
- 2) Justify why human flourishing and ethics of professions in social service are simultaneous formative components in engineering students when performing social service with this didactic model.
- 3) Demonstrate examples of prototypes that provide solutions to social problems as a result this social service.

It should be noted that the team of authors of this work, in addition to their teaching, administrative and research work, are part of the academic and administrative team that manages the *Semana Tec con Sentido Humano* (Tec Week with Human Sense) at the Monterrey Campus.

The Department of Humanistic Studies is assigned for scheduling groups, ensuring the accreditation and training of professors of this academic department to each group, assigning classrooms and schedules, providing didactic platforms for interaction, recording grades and hours of social services.

The Social Service Department has contact with the public or private non-profit organizations with which it will work, identifies their needs, designs the Canvas platform for the development of the course, the work agenda, theoretical content, didactic activities and quantitative and qualitative evaluation rubrics, before and after meetings with assigned professors, allocation of social service hours and follow-up on the implementation of the final projects, among other aspects.

Students from the 18 faculties of the School of Engineering register for the "*Semana Tec con Sentido Humano: Construcción de comunidades inclusivas desde la dignidad humana*".

2 Development

Tec de Monterrey's Educational Model is based on challenges (Tec de Monterrey 2016). The academic periods of Tecnológico de Monterrey in professional careers are made up of semesters that run from February to June, and from August to December; there are intensive winter courses in January, and summer courses in the month of July. The semesters are organized in 18 weeks, which are numbered from 1 to 18 for scheduling purposes. During weeks 6 and 12 of the semester students must take a Tec Week.

What is Tec Week? The Tec Week consists of an immersion of professional career students to conduct a challenge for the development of competencies that meet a need of the training partner in only five days. It is a period of five days equivalent to 8 units or hours of work each day, totaling 40 academic units or credits to develop specialty competencies or transversal competencies. The student can choose from a catalog of weeks but is obliged to take two Tec Weeks called "Tec Weeks with human sense" during his career.

And what is a Tec Week with human sense?

A Tec Week with Human Sense has the objective of developing the transversal competency Recognition and Empathy. By taking it, students collaborate in the concrete attention of a social problem, develop disciplinary and transversal competencies, with the accompaniment and punctual guidance of professors and training partners (Tapia 2021).

The training partner is a non-profit organization or body, public or private, that expresses one or more needs that the students could solve with the knowledge acquired so far in their professional career, and makes an agreement with Tec de Monterrey for which the students design a prototype or project for its solution.

Each Tec Week includes an agenda for reading and understanding theoretical frameworks related to the respective training purpose, spaces for at least two classroom dialogues or immersion in work field and moments for the design of the prototype or project according to the SlowU didactic methodology, which is a work culture that promotes values and practices with which we take the time to really understand social problems and from the collaborative, horizontal, inclusive and open work; effective proposals are designed to address a social need. For this, the methodology is guided by listening devices: unlearning, mapping and documentation with a field notebook, dialogue guides with the training partner for the projects and final proposal (Lafuente 2020) to finish with the delivery to the training partner of a prototype or final project. In each group of 35 students, groups of three to five students are integrated for their prototypes (Lafuente 2023). The Tec Week with human sense: building inclusive communities from human dignity aims to develop the transversal competence Recognition and Empathy which is defined as:

Respect the dignity, rights, contributions, personal circumstances and those of others, seeking to present constructive and supportive solutions to other people's situations.

Tec de Monterrey defines it as follows:

Respect the dignity, rights, contributions and personal circumstances and those of others, seeking to present constructive and supportive solutions to other people's situations. At this level, greater emphasis is placed on the second type of situation. To do the above, knowledge related to human dignity, empathy, human rights and sustainable development goals are mobilized; elements of the social, political, economic, cultural and environmental context are considered, as well as the development of the life project and the analysis of qualitative and quantitative information (Tec de Monterrey 2016). (Tec de Monterrey 2016).

The Tec Week: building inclusive communities based on human dignity was implemented at the Monterrey Campus and the rest of the Tecnológico de Monterrey campuses nationwide since August 2020.

The present work covers a demonstration that covers the periods from Aug-Dec 2022 to Feb-April 2025, totaling 13 Tec Weeks over six semesters where students at the School of Engineering apply their knowledge to concrete solutions to social problems. Based on this didactic model, the Social Service area, together with the School of Engineering, has a system for the production and follow-up of prototypes that endorse the students' social service hours, a process that had no empirical evidence of its results.

2.1 Theoretical basis of the didactic model

The Tec de Monterrey Educational Model (2016) is based on the development of competencies and through challenge-based learning.

In this Model, competency is understood as the conscious integration of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that allows successfully facing both structured and uncertain situations and that may involve higher order mental processes. Competency integrates both the knowledge and procedures of discipline, as well as the attitudes and values that allow the formation of participative professionals committed to society. In the TEC21 Educational Model there are two categories of competencies: discipline and transversal. Disciplinary competencies refer to all those knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that are considered necessary for professional practice. The development of disciplinary competencies implies a gradual construction that starts from the fundamental competencies to the terminal competencies of the discipline. On the other hand, transversal competencies are developed throughout the training process of any discipline, are useful for the graduate's life and have a direct impact on the quality of professional practice.

Challenge-Based Learning. In this same model, it is implemented through active learning from a Challenge-Based Learning approach, defined as: "It is a pedagogical approach that actively involves the student in a real, relevant and environmentally related problematic situation, which implies the definition of a challenge and the implementation of a solution. Challenge-based learning is based on experiential learning, which is based on the principle that students learn best when they actively participate in open learning experiences, rather than passively intervene in structured activities. In this sense, Experiential Learning offers students opportunities to apply what they learn in real situations, where they face problems, discover for themselves, try out solutions and interact with other students within a given context (Moore 2013). Experiential Learning is an integrative integrated approach to learning, combining experience, cognition and behavior (Akella 2010).

In this educational model, we agree with Francisco Ayala, who states that: "Along these lines, the professor's function is also that of an advisor who shows confidence and respect for the diverse possibilities of development of each of his students, which moves him to seek the most effective way for them to achieve integral development" (Ayala 2002).

The identification of the challenges for the development of transversal competencies and learning experiences is done through a dialogue between the teaching team and the representatives of a public or private entity called "Training Partner" about the needs that the students would help to solve. A protocol or Academic Collaboration Agreement is signed, with the previous authorization of the Academic Department Direction, and then the general objective and specific objectives are defined, both for students and professors.

2.2 Theoretical underpinnings of human flourishing

It is assumed that through Tec Week with Human Sense: Building communities from human dignity, engineering students stimulate human flourishing through social service in which they put together their talent and disciplinary knowledge acquired up to that moment to solve a real social problem and feel themselves active collaborators in the mission and objectives of the assigned training partner.

Generally, human flourishing is a concept associated with mature people, or university graduates, who discover it, aware that they are already at an age or period of their lives worthy of attention or discovery for better community living.

Is it possible to discover it from the university formation? To do something for others or for the community from the university formation? It is affirmed that yes, by means of the Social Service through the design of the Tec Week with human sense.

According to Tecnológico de Monterrey (2024), human flourishing:

It is a personal and conscious process of developing capacities in all areas of life, in which each person relates to the community and the environment to create a better world, respecting his or her own dignity and that of others... [even when carried out in community] the person is the center. It is a conscious process that responds to personal convictions, purpose and action. It is a process interrelated with the conditions of the social and environmental context.

The professor must be aware of his own human flourishing also stimulate it in his students integrated to the didactic processes within the university environment, which is to say, in the classroom or laboratory.

Therefore, the teaching activity should be complemented with the integration of cultural, cathartic and personal harmony aspects to be able to give oneself to others enjoying personal harmony in all senses.

2.3 Theoretical basis of Social Service in applied engineering ethics

What is intended for engineering students with Social Service (SS)? Why should SS be an opportunity for Applied Ethics? It is intended that students build and feel their own horizon of fulfillment and fulfillment within a framework of autonomy, and at the same time within the social and cultural groups to which they belong in the community. According to (Xteberria 2002), the Aristotelian Approach to ethics emphasizes the importance of the development of virtues, and affirms that the best way to learn virtues is through imitation; in universities, by tradition, professors are the model to imitate for young people, hence the importance of the teaching staff's active involvement in the SS. On the other hand, the Epicurean approach to ethics perceives as a purpose a decrease of pain and increase of pleasure among human beings, therefore, the healthiest thing is to create a pact of convenience among all, so that, as a group, and not individually, the least pain and the greatest pleasure for the most possible is achieved; that is why the SS aims to promote the collective good, rather than the particular. From a utilitarian approach, an ethical dilemma arises between considering a greater number of beneficiaries vs. a smaller number of non-beneficiaries, so that before a given act or decision, the dignity of all should always be respected equally, and not only favor a few people or cultural groups, leaving others discriminated from a benefit. By relating the three ethical approaches briefly mentioned with the students' SS, it will be possible to arrive directly at what Etxeberria calls a shared Happiness, that is, the one that arises at the moment in which the human being applies his own ethics and promotes for others and for himself that shared happiness, turning it into solidarity; solidarity of the student towards his environment and in this way it will be possible to move from daily experiences of SS to vital experiences of ethical internalization. In addition, it is possible for professors and educational institutions to get their students to make a moral reflection.

Social service in universities. In addition to the teaching of knowledge and values, it should be the duty of higher education institutions to promote through teaching the practice of those skills that prepare students to face various situations that require complex mental processes in their academic performance and later in the real world of building a professional career. In accordance with the Educational Model of Tecnológico de Monterrey, the Social Service promotes the practice of volunteering by students to fulfill their duties to society as professionals and citizens. This model was complemented with the approach of the Service Learning model proposed by the Polytechnic University of Valencia (2020) in which they state that: "Service

Learning is a teaching methodology that allows the training of students by putting the theoretical contents of the classroom at the service of society" in which, in addition to a methodology, this project requires a work protocol, in which the professors involved, after authorization from the Direction of their Department, agree with the non-profit entities, public or private, with which they will carry out this didactic experience.

3 Implementation of Tec Week with human sense

In August 2019, the implementation of the Tec21 Model began at Tecnológico del Monterrey. This model seeks to move from a traditionalist education-teaching to a new training based on learning challenges. This model, beyond only seeking to impact the professional training of students, also highlights the need for human sense within the new generations. Therefore, through the Social Service it manages to place the personal talent of each of the participants at the service of others.

The Social Service develops in the students' transversal and disciplinary competencies through the attention of specific needs of the communities, allowing them to acquire social service hours.

As part of their training, students participate in the following didactic experiences, each with its own pedagogical model: Tec Week of Induction to Social Service, Tec Week with Human Sense with the following thematic areas: Integrity, Zero Hunger, Inclusive Communities, Climate Emergency, and Philanthropy. Other models with similar purposes, but with five weeks of duration are: Human Sense Block, Social Immersion, and Project Solidarity. For the purposes of this paper, only the Semana Tec con Sentido Humano will be addressed, specifically in the thematic area of inclusive communities. A Tec Week has a working duration of one week, which is offered in two moments within the semester periods and where students collaborate hand in hand with a professor and a civil society organization to address social causes related to the thematic area offered. The Tec Week with a focus on Inclusive Communities seeks to promote the development and recognition of human dignity to build safe and inclusive communities while promoting inclusion, gender equality and strengthening practices that benefit them.

To guarantee a good implementation of the Tec Week, there is a Tec Week agenda that is communicated to the students from the beginning as a crucial element in the Canvas electronic platform. Interaction with the training partner can be face-to-face or remotely via the zoom platform, teams or meet.

Figure 1. Work agenda of the *Semana Tec son sentido humano*.

The instances involved for this training unit are: The 18 academic departments of the School of Engineering, the Department of Humanistic Studies and the Department of Social Service. The theoretical frameworks of this Tec Week cover the following topics: 1. What does it mean to recognize human dignity? a) Why talk about human dignity. 2. Discover diversity: a) What are unconscious biases, b) Diversity and inclusion, and c) Gender perspective.

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Table 1. Below are indicators from the August-December 2022 semester to date of the interaction, information, results and progress that have been made in this Tec Week with human sense: Building inclusive communities based on human dignity.

Period	Week	Groups	Students	Prototypes	Focus on Engineering
August-December 2022	Week 6	3	113	19	0
	Week 12	2	43	8	2
February-June 2023	Week 6	6	176	36	6
	Week 12	5	142	28	3
August-December 2023	Week 6	7	213	78	10
	Week 12	9	217	32	4
February-June 2024	Week 6	19	494	99	18
	Week 12	15	376	83	17
August-December 2024	Week 6	4	120	26	5
	Week 12	3	65	14	1
February-June 2025	Week 6	14	422	47	5
	Week 12 *				
Totals:		87	2,381	470	71

*Week to be held from May 5 to May 9

Interpretation: There are 71 prototypes focused on the solution of a social problem from the careers of the School of Engineering; to validate their feasibility, the evaluation method consists of two moments: during the Tec Week, specifically in the collaborative spaces within the agenda entitled "moments of service" 1. Validation and start of prototype, and 2. Subsequently, the prototypes are delivered to the organizations for immediate implementation. And as the last part of the method, feedback or comments are received from the training partner on the implemented prototypes, and those that obtained the most outstanding results are identified.

The 41 participating organizations or training partners during the periods mentioned are listed below: ACNUR, ALZ Monterrey, ANSPAC, Asociación de Psicólogos de Nuevo León, AWAQ ONGD, Best Buddies de México A.C., CADHAC, Campamentos Tec Casa Hogar Refugio 121, Casanicolás, Centro de Entrenamiento Acuático, Ecoaldeas del Norte, Edumakers, Enseña por México, FICAE, FONDEAGG, Fundación El Mundo Escribe, Fundación Salvador Vida México, Género, ética y salud sexual AC, Inclusión Tec, Instituto Down, Instituto Nuevo Amanecer, Lazos que transforman, LGBTIQ WORLD, A.C., MAFI, Magis Fidem, A.C., Misión del Nayar, Oídos valientes PowerChair, Salud Mental para Indigentes A.C., Secretaría de Igualdad e Inclusión de Nuevo León, Sonrisas de Cristal, Soy Plena, Tutores de Resiliencia, UNAC, Unidos, Vercodi, Viccali, VIFAC, VIDUSA.

The following is a virtual resource where the 71 prototypes focused on the engineering area can be viewed, divided into a) the visualization of the prototype; and b) the documentation that is the theoretical support of the prototype.

As a sampling of these works, all equally important, we suggest identifying the following: *EdumakersRED*, *Inclusive Voices*, *Instructional Matching*, *R-ACNUR* and *Sustentrack*:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Enc1mrvZsooqzJ3PXwH4R5cMfbOviUGQ?usp=sharing>

Table 2. Engineering students during the period Aug-Dec 2022 to Feb-April 2025.

Total students in <i>Semana Tec con sentido humano: Construcción de comunidades inclusivas desde la dignidad humana</i> (Tec Week with human sense: Building inclusive communities based on human dignity) in the indicated period.	Students at the School of Engineering	Percentage
2381	887	37.25%

Interpretation: The participation of students from the School of Engineering this Tec Week in engineering students is 37.25 percent.

The engineering careers most involved with these products are Data Science and Mathematics Engineering, Robotics and Digital Systems Engineering, Industrial and Systems Engineering, Mechatronics Engineering, Computer Technologies Engineering, Civil Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Biomedical Engineering.

4 Evaluation of results

The initial research assumption was favorably verified: Students of engineering careers discover their human flourishing from their university stage when performing a social service with the didactic design of the "*Semana Tec con sentido humano: construcción de comunidades inclusivas desde la dignidad humana*", and, simultaneously, they develop the transversal competence of recognition and empathy; both elements will shape their professional profile when they enter the working world with their professional degree.

Student feedback. To learn about the students' experience within the Tec Weeks, a feedback survey was applied to the most recent Week the March 17-21, 2025, with the following result:

Universe: 1,987 participated in the survey, participation rate 56.94%.

62.46% mentioned that they became aware of the social needs of their community, the country and the world.

57.40% believe that their prototype/project will have a positive impact on today's society.

On a Likert scale where 5 is the highest and 1 is the lowest students were asked the following questions:

Satisfaction with the didactic design of the Tech Week: 49.86/5

Testimony of the training partner *Amigos de la Sierra*: "Thank you very much for the opportunity! It was an extraordinary experience; I enjoyed it very much... I hope we can continue collaborating" and the training partner *100enundía*: "Thank you very much for the invitation... The truth is that the experience was quite interesting, since the ideas of some of the students were creative and hit the nail on the head in what I was looking for".

5 Conclusions

Interdisciplinary work within universities is important for an educational and didactic project with the same objective. With the 71 prototypes of eight engineering schools in the states of Nuevo León, Chihuahua, and Mexico City in Mexico; and in Bogotá, Colombia, the research assumption was demonstrated and the general objective and the three specific objectives presented at the beginning of this work were achieved, thus validating and consolidating that the didactic design of the Tec Week with Human Sense: Construction of inclusive communications from human dignity stimulates human flourishing from the university life of future engineers developing the transversal competence Recognition and empathy within a horizon of plenitude by consciously making available to others their talent and knowledge for a shared happiness, a trait that will seal it in their future professional performance. Greater interdisciplinary communication between engineering and humanities professors is detonated since the teaching and follow-up of this Tec Week is conducted with the collaboration of both areas.

¡Sembremos!

Sembremos y dejemos a

la atmósfera moral que haga el resto,

como el labrador confía a la lluvia,

al aire y al sol sus semillas.

Aremos el suelo de la sociedad,

removiéndolo; agitámosla y sembremos

luego en ella ideas, abnegadamente,

sin pensar en nosotros mismos.

Lo demás vendrá con el tiempo.

Miguel de Unamuno

España, 1927

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